

OF ENERGY DRINKS ON CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

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Abstract

This article describes in detail the effect of energy drinks, one of the most popular soft drinks, on the working mechanism of the heart, muscle contraction, pulse, and blood composition. Due to the increase in energy drink consumption over the past decade, the number of energy drink users among emergency room responders has also increased significantly. That is, alcohol poisoning, arrhythmia, increased blood pressure and heart rate are observed. In order to observe these effects, we conducted a study among our peers.

Keywords: Energy drinks, caffeine, taurine , Cardiovascular effects: arrhythmia , adrenaline, Baum and Weiss study, sugar, insulin, Red Bull.

Relevance Energetic drinks in the world the most publicize gan without alcohol from drinks one di r (1). Energetic drinks surface which brings different different pathological processes as a result one how many in organs different diseases surface comes , (5) that including in the heart also(2). 1 box sugar with provided energetic drink (355 ml drink volume) consumption to do to the heart the work of download to increase take to come , this while blood pressure and heart hit of speed increase with confirmed . Heart blood vessel in the system surface coming from diseases

exactly energetic drinks to drink as a result surface coming diseases (3) whole the world in the community relatively fast way grow up going with from the day to the day of the century current from problems to one turning around going on (4).

Material and methods : Tashkent city , Tashkent medicine academy many p network clinic 9th building Rheumacardiology in the department lying down 35 patients under treatment information analysis done .

The goal : Energetic of drinks heart work mechanism effect as a result surface coming diseases and their complications population between spread level assessment

Results : Scientific research 35 at work person heart arrhythmia and myocardium infarction disease with being treated patients young range from 40 years old small and from the age of 40 big to patients we separated .

Diagram-1. Energetic drink complication according to analysis ;

Diagram-2. Sex according to analysis .

Separately received 6 of the patients myocardium heart attack , 2 people while heart arrhythmia with that it hurts study as a result we determined . Separately 6 received

from the patient myocardium infarction disease with played 1 of the patients a woman , and 5 of them male that let's see can So EU consumption to women relatively in men more is meeting

Summary : Har one from the norm more than drunk energetic drink your your health for harmful is considered Energetic drinks consumption in doing known norms that it was not and their effect complete and deep unstudied because of them less amount consumption to do or Entirely consumption not to do recommendation will be done . You have surface coming possible to your health risk that puts some one to diseases inclinations surface to bring and above telling passed heart-blood vein system to diseases you play danger existence because of energetic drinks consumption reduce your you for we consider it beneficial .

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